

Supplementary 1. Parental consent

Re: The effectiveness of silver diamine fluoride treatment with different post-treatment protocols in arresting dental caries in primary teeth of preschool children

Dear parents:

Your child is being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

Faculty of Dentistry of The University of Hong Kong is now conducting a clinical study among preschool children. The aim of this study is to assess the effectiveness of the 38% SDF application in stopping decayed teeth over 12 months, when two different post-treatment instructions were used. Approximately 254 children with decayed teeth will be invited to join. There is no serious side effect reported in the literature. The successfully arrested carious lesion will turn black and hard; and this is a common outcome for successful treatment. Please note that there will be no dark staining on sound teeth.

The details of the activity would be as follows:

- Target: K1 students.
- Proposed period: The research will be launched in the first half of 2023; Oral examination and intervention will be provided biannually for 12 months.
- Activities: (1) oral health education; (2) parental questionnaire survey; (3) oral examination; (4) 38% SDF treatment

These activities will be carried out in the kindergarten. If child has tooth decay, he/she will be randomly allocated to receive SDF treatment with different groups: Group A –to rinse their teeth immediately after SDF treatment. Group B –not to eat and drink for at least 30 minutes. During the dental examination, no radiography will be taken. Each participating child will receive a report on the oral health. Children who need any other dental services such as extraction can be treated by a dentist at their own cost.

If you decide to take part in the study, please fill in the questionnaire attached and authorize us to provide a dental examination to your children in school time. The oral examination and treatment will take 1 to 2 minutes. No lifestyle or dietary restriction is required during the study period. You are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive in the future.

You have the right to access personal data and publicly available study results, if needed. Under the laws of Hong Kong (the Personal Data (Privacy) Ordinance, Cap 486), you enjoy or may enjoy rights for the protection of the confidentiality of your personal data, such as those regarding the collection, custody, retention, management, control, use (including analysis or comparison), transfer in or out of Hong Kong, non-disclosure, erasure and/or in any way dealing with or disposing of any of your personal data in or for this study. For any query, you should consult the Privacy Commissioner for Personal Data or their office (Tel No. 2827 2827) as to the proper monitoring or supervision of your personal data protection so that your full awareness and

understanding of the significance of compliance with the law governing privacy data is assured.

By consenting to take part in this study, you expressly authorize:

- a) the principal investigator and his research team and the ethics committee (Institutional Review Board of the University of Hong Kong / Hospital Authority Hong Kong West Cluster) responsible for overseeing this study to get access to, to use, and to retain your personal data for the purposes and in the manner described in this informed consent process; and
- b) the relevant government agencies (e.g., the Hong Kong Department of Health) to get access to your personal data for the purposes of checking and verifying the integrity of study data and assessing compliance with the study protocol and relevant requirements.

It is possible that when taking part in the oral examination, your child may feel discomfort. If your child is too unwilling to be checked, the oral examination will stop immediately. Follow-up examination will be conducted, and medical advice will be given if there are any adverse effects related to the treatment.

If your child is harmed due to someone's negligence, then you may have grounds for a legal action. Regardless of this, if you wish to complain about any aspect of the way your child has been approached during this study, the University of Hong Kong's complaints mechanisms may be available to you.

After examination, each of the participants will receive a set of souvenirs. We hope that the oral examination will help you to understand the oral health status of your child. This study is self-funded and has been reviewed by Institutional Review Board of the University of Hong Kong / Hospital Authority Hong Kong West Cluster. If you have any enquiry, please contact Prof. Chu Chun Hung at 2859 0287 during office hours. Please complete the following consent if you agree to participate in this study. Thank you very much.

Yours faithfully,

Dr. Duangthip Duangporn, Prof. Chu Chun Hung
Faculty of Dentistry, The University of Hong Kong.

PATIENT/SUBJECT CONSENT FORM

Child name: _____

Title of Project: **The effectiveness of silver diamine fluoride treatment with different post-treatment protocols in arresting dental caries in primary teeth of preschool children**

Name of Researcher: Dr. Duangthip Duangporn, Prof. Chu Chun Hung

Please tick ✓ in the box

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw any time, without giving any reason, without my medical care or legal rights being affected.

3. I understand that sections of any of my medical notes may be looked at by responsible individuals from Faculty of Dentistry, The University of Hong Kong or from Institutional Review Board of the University of Hong Kong / Hospital Authority Hong Kong West Cluster.

I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records.

4. Regarding this one-year study:

4.1. I agree to let my child undergo oral examination and fluoride treatment;

4.2. I agree to complete the questionnaire;

4.3. I agree to have photos taken of the teeth of my child (not including face) to record the change of decayed teeth.

Name of Parent / Guardian

Date

Signature

Researcher

Date

Signature

HKU Dentistry

Faculty of Dentistry · The University of Hong Kong

香港大學牙醫學院